

Theoretical interaction of epoxybergamoti, hyperforin and hypericin with Cyp3A4 and P-glycoprotein using a theoretical model

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Abstract

Some chemical components involved in grapefruit juice and St. John's wort can produce changes in pharmacological activity of different drugs; however, their interaction with both P-glycoprotein and CyP450 enzyme is not clear. The aim of this study was to evaluate the possible interaction of epoxybergamoti, hyperforin and hypericin with both P-glycoprotein and CyP450 enzyme using 1w0f, 3g5u proteins, midazolam, simvastatin and fexofenadine as theoretical tools in DockingServer program. The results showed differences in the aminoacid residues involved in the interaction of epoxybergamoti, hyperforin and hypericin with 1w0f, 3g5u proteins surface compared with midazolam, simvastatin and fexofenadine. Besides, inhibition (K_i) constant for hyperforin was lower compared with epoxybergamottin and hypericin. Other data, displayed that K_i for epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin was lower compared with fexofenadine. In conclusion, the results suggest that; 1) hyperforin could act as CyP3A4 inhibitor; 2) epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin could act as P-glycoprotein blocker. This phenomenon suggests that the concomitant use of the chemical components of grapefruit juice and St. John's wort with midazolam, fexofenadine and simvastatin could produce changes in the pharmacological activity of midazolam, simvastatin and fexofenadine.

Keywords: Grapefruit juice and St. John's wort, Epoxybergamottin, Hyperforin, Hypericin.

1. Introduction

In the literature there are several studies on interaction drug-drug which may produce some secondary effects [1-6]. It is important to mention that also drug-food interactions could produce changes in pharmacological activity of some drugs through of changes in gastrointestinal pH [7], alter gastrointestinal motility [8], produce changes in some transport proteins and this phenomenon could be translated as changes of bioavailability of some drugs [9]. For example, a study showed that the bioavailability of cyclosporine increases with the consumption of grapefruit juice (240 ml), as the duration of cyclosporine effect can last up to 24 hours. [10]. Furthermore, a pharmacokinetic study showed that administration concomitant of triazolam (25 mg) and grapefruit juice (250 ml) oral route increase triazolam plasma concentrations [11]. Other data indicate that the administration of midazolam (CYP3A4 substrate) in combination with grapefruit juice may cause drowsiness and prolonged sedation [12, 13]. This interaction could be conditioned by CYP3A4 inhibition; this hypothesis is supported by some studies which indicate that some chemical components involved grapefruit juice are furanocoumarins such as bergamottin and epoxybergamotin, 6',7'-dihydroxy-bergamotin, which act as CYP3A4 inhibitors [14, 15]. In addition, a study conducted with healthy volunteers who took 200 ml of grapefruit juice and 60 mg of simvastatin showed that grapefruit juice significantly increased serum concentrations of simvastatin through CYP3A4 inhibition [16]. Other data indicate that grapefruit juice increases felodipine oral availability in humans by decreasing intestinal CYP3A protein expression [17] and this effect could be that epoxybergamottin enhanced the oral bioavailability of felodipine [18].

On the other hand, a study carried out in heart transplant patients showed that the concomitant use of cyclosporine (immunosuppressive drug) [19] and St. John's wort decreases plasma levels of cyclosporine (CYP3A4 P-glycoprotein substrate) [20-22]. Besides, other data showed that the association of nevirapine (CYP2B6 and Cyp3A4 inducer) with St. John's wort could decrease the antiviral activity due increasing its clearance [23]. Another report displayed that administration of St. John's wort with tacrolimus (immunosuppressive drug) may produce nephrotoxicity unmasked through

CYP3A4 activation [24]. However, a study showed that St. John's wort appears to induce tacrolimus metabolism, most likely through induction of both CYP3A and P-glycoprotein systems [25]. Another report indicate that St. John's wort modulate P-glycoprotein transport activity in Blood-Brain Barrier [26]; these differences could involve some chemical constituents involved in St. John's wort such as hypericin and hyperforin [27]. Besides, a study showed that hyperforin and hypericin, inhibit the active efflux of the fluorescent markers daunorubicin [28]. Other data showed that capsaicin increases the daunorubicin and rhodamine levels through P-glycoprotein inhibition in KB-C2 cells using an analytic method [29]. Finally, a study showed that capsaicin pretreatment significantly enhanced the intestinal absorption and bioavailability of fexofenadine (selective histamine H₁-receptor antagonist) in rats likely by inhibition of P-glycoprotein mediated cellular efflux [30]. All these data indicate that epoxybergamotin can produce changes in biological activity of Cyp3A4 enzyme. Besides, epoxybergamoti can interact with P-glycoprotein; however, their interaction with this biomolecules is not clear. Analyzing these data the aim of this research was to evaluate the interaction of epoxybergamoti, hyperforin and hypericin with both P-glycoprotein and Cyp3A4 enzyme.

2. Material and Methods

Chemical components involved in some foods such as hyperforin, hypericin, epoxybergamottin were used to evaluate their possible interaction with both P-glycoprotein and Cyp3A4 enzyme as follows:

Figure 1: Chemical structure of epoxybergamottin (A), hyperforin (B) and hypericin (C).

Source: Authors.

2.1 Protein-Ligand complex

Interaction analysis of midazolam, simvastatin, fexofenadine, hyperforin, hypericin, epoxybergamottin, daunorubicin and rhodamine with either 3g5u (doi.org/10.2210/pdb3G5U/pdb) or 1w0f (doi.org/10.2210/pdb1W0F/pdb) proteins using Docking-Server program [31]

2.2 Thermodynamic parameters

The energy levels involved in protein-ligand complex formation were determined using DockingServer program [31]

3. Results and Discussion

To predict the food-drug interaction, several methods have been used, including spectroscopic analysis [32], pharmacophore development, quantitative structure-activity relationships, and docking models [33]. In this research, a theoretical analysis on interaction from chemical

components involved in some foods was conducted using DockingServer program.

3.1 Ligand-Cyp 3A4 complex

There are some reports on computer-aided modeling on Cytochrome P450-mediated food-drug interactions [34-36]. However, the interaction of epoxybergamottin, hypericin and hyperforin with Cyp3A4 enzyme is not clear. For this reason, the interaction of this compounds with Cyp3A4 enzyme was evaluated using 1w0f protein as theoretical tool. Besides, two substrates for Cyp3A4 enzyme (midazolam and simvastatin) [37, 38] were used as controls in DockingServer program. The results showed differences in the aminoacid residues involved in the interaction of epoxybergamottin, Hyperforin, Hypericin with 1w0f protein surface compared with both midazolam, simvastatin, Figure (1) and Table (1).

Figure 1. Aminoacid residues involved in the interaction of epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 1w0f protein surface. Visualized with DockingServer program.

Source: Authors.

Table 1. Theoretical interaction of midazolam, simvastatin, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 1wOf protein surface.

Compound	Aminoacid Residues
Midazolam	Lys ₂₀₉ ; Phe ₂₁₃ ; Asp ₂₁₇ ; Phe ₂₁₉ ; Phe ₂₂₀ ; Val ₂₄₀ ; Pro ₂₄₂
Simvastatine	Leu ₂₁₀ ; Phe ₂₁₃ ; Asp ₂₁₄ ; Asp ₂₁₇ ; Phe ₂₁₉ ; Phe ₂₂₀ ; Val ₂₄₀ ; Pro ₂₄₂
Epoxybergamottin	Leu ₂₁₁ ; Phe ₂₁₃ ; Asp ₂₁₄ ; Phe ₂₂₀ ; Pro ₂₄₂
Hyperforin	Lys ₂₀₉ ; Phe ₂₁₃ ; Asp ₂₁₇ ; Phe ₂₁₉ ; Phe ₂₂₀ ; Ile ₂₃₈ ; Val ₂₄₀ ; Pro ₂₄₂
Hypericin	Lys ₂₀₉ ; Phe ₂₁₃ ; Phe ₂₁₉ ; Phe ₂₂₀ ; Ile ₂₃₈ ; Val ₂₄₀ ; Pro ₂₄₂

Source: Authors.

3.2 Ligand-(P)glycoprotein analysis

Some methods have used to predict the food-drug via P-glycoprotein inhibition [39-41]. In this study, a theoretical analysis was conducted to evaluate the interaction of fexofenadine, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 3g5u protein surface. The results displayed different aminoacid residues for Epoxybergamottin (Thr₁₆₉; Leu₈₈₆; Glu₈₈₇), hyperforin (Ala₂₄₄; Ala₂₄₈; Glu₂₅₁; Thr₈₁₁; Ala₈₁₅; Asn₈₁₆), hypericin (Thr₈₉₄), Daunorubicin (Asp₆₈₅; Glu₆₈₆; Asp₆₈₇; Lys₉₉₆) compared with fexofenadine, Figure (2) and Table (2).

Figure 2. Interaction of epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 3g5u protein surface. Visualized with DockingServer program.

Source: Authors.

Table 2: Theoretical interaction of fexofenadine, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 3g5u protein surface.

Compound	Aminoacid Residues
Fexofenadine	Thr ₁₇₂ ; Asp ₁₇₃ ; Ser ₁₇₆ ; Lys ₁₇₇ ; Glu ₁₈₀ ; Lys ₈₈₃ ; Leu ₈₈₆
Epoxybergamottin	Thr ₁₆₉ ; Thr ₁₇₂ ; Asp ₁₇₃ ; Leu ₈₈₆ ; Glu ₈₈₇
Hyperforin	Ala ₂₄₄ ; Ala ₂₄₈ ; Glu ₂₅₁ ; Thr ₈₁₁ ; Thr ₈₁₂ ; Ala ₈₁₅ ; Asn ₈₁₆
Hypericin	Asn ₁₆₈ ; Thr ₁₆₉ ; Thr ₁₇₂ ; Asp ₁₇₃ ; Thr ₈₉₄

Source: Authors.

3.3 Thermodynamic analysis

For several years, different types of methods such as isothermal titration calorimetry [26], quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics [27], termott [28] and DockingServer [23] have been used to calculate the binding energy involved in protein-ligand complex formation. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate some thermodynamic factors involved in the interaction of epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 1w0f protein using midazolam, simvastatine as

controls. The results displayed differences in the thermodynamic parameters involved in the interaction of epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin compared to midazolam and simvastatine. In addition, the inhibition constant (Ki) for epoxybergamottin and hypericin was higher compared to compared to midazolam and simvastatine, Table (3); however, the Ki for hyperforin was lower compared with epoxybergamottin and hypericin. These results suggest that hyperforin could have contact with 1w0f protein surface and this phenomenon could be translated as a good Cyp3A4 inhibitor.

On the other hand, the analysis on the interaction of fexofenadine, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with the 3g5u protein showed differences in energy levels for each of these compounds. Besides, the Ki for epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin was lower compared with fexofenadine, Table (4). These data suggest that epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin may act as P-glycoprotein inhibitors and this phenomenon suggest that epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin could produce changes in biological activity of P-glycoprotein.

Table 3. Thermodynamic values for midazolam, simvastatin, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 1w0f protein surface.

Compounds	A	B	C	D	E	F
Midazo-lam	-7.0	7.0	-7.3	-0.03	-7.3	571.8
Simvastatine	-7.3	3.9	-8.7	-0.03	-8.7	685.2
Epoxybergamottin	-5.3	113.5	-5.6	0.00	-5.6	552.0
Hyperforin	-6.6	12.8	-8.7	0.05	-8.6	785.4
Hypericin	-9.0	253.9	-6.7	-0.10	-6.8	692.6

Note: **A** = Est: Free Energy of Binding (kcal/mol); **B** = Inhibition Constant, Ki (mM); **C** = vdW + Hbond + desolv Energy (kcal/mol); **D** = Electrostatic Energy (kcal/mol); **E** = Total Intermolec. Energy (kcal/mol); **F** = Interact. Surface; Exam = exametene; Form = formostene. **Source:** Authors.

Table 4. Thermodynamic values for Fexofenadine, epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with 3g5u protein surface.

Compounds	A	B	C	D	E	F
Fexofenadine	-4.3	709.3	-3.91	-0.83	-4.7	552.1
Epoxybergamottin	-3.6	2.24	-3.85	-0.06	-3.9	596.6
Hyperforin	-2.5	14.38	-4,38	-0.22	-4.6	648.8
Hypericin	-6.6	12.64	-4.32	-0.48	-4.8	481.3

Note: **A** = Est: Free Energy of Binding (kcal/mol); **B** = Inhibition Constant, Ki (mM); **C** = vdW + Hbond + desolv Energy (kcal/mol); **D** = Electrostatic Energy (kcal/mol); **E** = Total Intermolec. Energy (kcal/mol); **F** = Interact. Surface; Exam = exametene; Form = formostene. **Source:** Authors.

4. Conclusions

In this study is reported the interaction of epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin with both Cyp3A4 and P-glycoprotein using as theoretical model. The result suggest that; 1) hyperforin could act as CyP3A4 inhibitor; 2) epoxybergamottin, hyperforin and hypericin could act as P-glycoprotein blocker. This phenomenon suggests that the concomitant use of the chemical components of grapefruit juice and St. John's wort with midazolam, fexofenadine and simvastatin could produce changes in the pharmacological activity of these drugs.

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